

Sustainable Development and Environmental Journalism: Implementing Societal Progress in Kazakhstan

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Abstract: The study aimed to explore how environmental journalism in Central Asia influences public opinion on environmental issues and sustainable development. It highlights that environmental journalism plays a crucial role in informing society about these critical topics. According to the World Bank's Climate and Environment Program, Kazakhstan has made notable progress in achieving sustainable development goals, particularly through initiatives like landscape restoration and sustainable forest management in regions such as Kyzylorda and Zhambyl¹⁹. However, the broader Central Asian region still requires concerted efforts to fully implement sustainable development strategies. The study emphasizes that quality and accessible information on environmental issues is vital for shaping public opinion and mobilizing citizens to address these challenges. Effective environmental journalism can bridge the gap between scientific research and public awareness, fostering a more engaged and informed society that is better equipped to tackle environmental issues and support sustainable development initiatives.

Keywords: digital technologies; environmental problems; overcoming crises; social media; shaping public opinion

1. Introduction

The study of the role of environmental journalism in the implementation of the concept of sustainable development of society has become necessary in the light of the growing environmental problems faced by the modern world. In this context, environmental journalism acts as an important tool for informing society about environmental problems, as well as a mechanism for stimulating public dialogue and taking the necessary measures to eliminate these problems. Since its inception in the early 20th century, environmental journalism has come a long way in its development, overcoming both technical and ideological challenges¹⁻³. Today, environmental journalism is at the intersection of scientific knowledge, social activism and the media, which makes it particularly important in the context of sustainable development. Existing challenges in the field include insufficient media coverage of environmental

topics, distorted perceptions of the state of the environment, and lack of public engagement in environmentally relevant decision-making processes. If these problems are not addressed, they may lead to further aggravation of environmental crises, loss of biodiversity, deterioration of the quality of human life and even threaten the survival of humanity as a whole⁴.

The role of the mass media in creating awareness of environmental issues and changing societal behaviour with respect to climate change, biodiversity, and energy efficiency has been examined in studies by G. Mocatta⁵ and B. Gezmen⁶. G. Mocatta stated the need for in-depth coverage of environmental issues and their impact on biodiversity, and B. Gezmen reviewed the role of environmental journalism in raising awareness of energy efficiency and pointed out the real opportunity to improve energy efficiency through active media engagement. The influence of different types of media frames on consumer

behaviour and decision-making regarding climate change and energy efficiency is a relevant issue that requires more detailed consideration and research in the future.

Another important issue in the study area, understanding behavioural responses to changing environments and the role of media in shaping environmental consciousness, has been highlighted by A. Misra⁷⁾ and T.M. Marteau et al.⁸⁾ In the study of A. Misra, the author revealed the importance of the media's role in increasing environmental awareness and shaping public opinion about environmental issues, including its influence on people's behaviour and environmentally responsible decision-making. T.M. Marteau et al., in turn, presented an analysis of the relationship between environmental change and modification of human behavioural patterns. A deeper understanding of the mechanisms of interaction between the environment, human behaviour and the role of mass media in the formation of environmental consciousness requires further study of this issue.

The influence of journalism on shaping perceptions of sustainable development and addressing global environmental issues has been studied by scholars such as D. Atanasova⁹⁾, S. Janoušková et al.¹⁰⁾, M. Brüggemann et al.¹¹⁾. The results of the work of D. Atanasova showed that the use of a consistent, optimistic, credible and structural narrative in the context of sustainable development contributes to society's motivation for change and the adoption of sustainable practices. S. Janoušková et al.¹⁰⁾ focused on the problems of communication of the concept of sustainable development by mass media and pointed out the insufficient coverage of sustainable development topics in news and information programmes, which makes it difficult to achieve.

The gaps in the reviewed studies pointed to the unexplored nature of environmental journalism in the Central Asian region and a number of challenges in the field of environmental awareness and the role of media in the world. The aim of this study is to examine the methods of environmental journalism's influence in the Central Asia on the formation of public opinion on environmental and sustainable development issues¹¹⁾. The objectives of the study included reviewing the principles and methods of environmental journalism, analysing the impact of journalistic activities on public consciousness, examining the key factors that determine the effectiveness of journalists' work in this area, and identifying the limitations and challenges faced by journalists in covering environmental topics.

2. Materials and Methods

This theoretical study explored in detail the concept of environmental journalism and its impact on shaping public opinion on environmental and sustainable development issues. The first stage of the work covered a wide range of

topics and issues addressed by environmental journalism, including environmental disasters, climate change, air, water and soil pollution, as well as natural resource management and environmentally responsible decision-making. It also analysed existing media types, ranging from traditional media such as newspapers, magazines and television, to online platforms and social media, and the types of publications in them, including: special columns, programmes, news articles, blogs and online portals.

Another significant step for the study was to examine various aspects of the impact of environmental journalism on public consciousness, including informing policymakers, raising awareness and empathy, changing readers' behaviour towards the environment, promoting sustainable practices and influencing corporate behaviour. The study of this aspect has identified the most effective ways of presenting information. Key factors determining the effectiveness of environmental journalists were examined, including cooperation with the scientific community, fact-checking, interpretation of scientific research and ethical considerations. Particular attention was paid to the limitations and complications journalists face in reporting on environmental issues, such as access to information, subjectivity in evaluating the work of researchers and the need for ethical standards, revealing the methods and approaches of environmental journalism to encourage dialogue and compromise.

The next stage of the study explored current trends in the development of environmental journalism, including the use of new media technologies and the influence of social and political factors on media coverage of environmental issues. The work also examined examples of successful environmental journalism from different countries and regions of the world, revealing key factors that can contribute to improving the work of environmental journalists, including strengthening cooperation with the scientific community, raising public awareness and actively using modern information technologies^{12,13)}.

As part of the SDG review, a number of materials were reviewed, including the reports "Billions globally lack 'water, sanitation and hygiene', new UN report spells out"¹⁴⁾, "Central Asian countries discussed progress in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals at a high-level summit in Almaty"¹⁵⁾, "Sustainable Development Goals progress chart"¹⁶⁾, "The Sustainable Development Goals report: Special edition"¹⁷⁾, "Progress towards the Sustainable Development Goals: Towards a rescue plan for people and planet" by United Nations Secretary-General¹⁸⁾, "Goal 1: End poverty in all its forms everywhere"¹⁹⁾, "WHO and UNICEF launch updated estimates for water, sanitation, and hygiene"²⁰⁾, "Child mortality and causes of death" World Health Organization²¹⁾, "The 11 biggest hurdles for women's equality by 2030"²²⁾, "250 million children out-of-school: What you need to know about UNESCO's latest education

data"¹²), "New UNESCO report shows extent of global inequalities in education and calls for greater inclusion as schools re-open"²³) and "CAREC 2030: Connecting the region for shared and sustainable development"²⁴), "Women and girls"²⁵), "This is why many young people have no access to proper education"²⁶).

The study prioritized sources that discuss environmental journalism, its impact, and related topics such as climate change, pollution, and sustainable development. This focus ensured that the information was directly relevant to the study's objectives. Additionally, the study included various media types such as newspapers, magazines, television, online platforms, and social media. This diversity allowed for a comprehensive analysis of how different media channels address environmental issues. To provide a global perspective, the study incorporated examples and case studies from different countries and regions, highlighting both universal and region-specific challenges and solutions in environmental journalism. Sources that discuss recent trends and developments in environmental journalism were also prioritized. This emphasis on current information ensured that the study reflected the latest advancements and challenges in the field. Furthermore, official reports and materials related to the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) were included, particularly those that highlight progress and challenges in achieving these goals. This inclusion provided a robust framework for evaluating the effectiveness of environmental journalism in promoting sustainable development.

Sources that did not directly relate to environmental journalism or sustainable development were excluded from the study. This criterion helped maintain a focused and relevant analysis. Outdated sources that did not reflect current practices or trends were also excluded. This ensured that the study's findings were based on the most recent and relevant information available.

Thus, statistical indicators and experts' assessments of sustainable development in such areas as poverty, child health and well-being, inequality in education, gender discrimination, water supply and sanitation, climate change and biodiversity loss, human rights violations and conflicts, and the effectiveness of SDG implementation in the Central Asian region were reviewed.

3. Results

Environmental journalism covers a wide range of topics and issues related to the state of the environment and the impact of human activity on nature. It explores and covers environmental disasters, climate change, air, water and soil pollution, the threat of species extinction, as well as natural resource management and environmentally responsible decision-making. Environmental journalism addresses issues related to ecological innovation, green technologies

and sustainable consumption and production practices, and examines the links between environmental issues and social, economic and political aspects of society.

Media dealing with environmental issues vary in format, type of publication and audience. Traditional media such as newspapers, magazines, and television offer extensive coverage of environmental issues through various columns, special issues and programmes²⁷). Online platforms and news sites are also becoming an important source of information on environmental issues, offering wide access to news, articles, and blogs. Social media play a growing role in the dissemination of environmental information, allowing users to share news, opinions, and shares in real-time^{28,29}). In addition, there are specialized media projects and organizations dedicated exclusively to environmental topics, environmental magazines, blogs and online portals that offer in-depth analysis, expert opinions and research on conservation issues.

Environmental journalism actively engages with the scientific community, the public and other stakeholders to ensure the accuracy and reliability of information and to stimulate public dialogue and action on environmental issues. One method of engaging with the scientific community is to use scientific research and expert opinion as a source of information for journalistic stories. Journalists can consult with scientists to analyse data, interpret results and identify trends in the development of environmental issues. Public outreach includes disseminating information through various media formats such as print, television, radio, online portals and social media.

3.1. The impact of environmental journalism on public opinion and behaviour

Environmental journalists make significant efforts to raise public awareness of environmental issues. They use a variety of methods and approaches that not only inform, but also evoke an emotional response and activate public action. One of the main methods is the use of living stories and examples that can be close and understandable to the audience. Journalists try to select and report on events and phenomena that occur close to where people live and in their daily lives. This could be an investigation into the pollution of water bodies in a region, a story about agricultural areas affected by climate change, or the problems of sorting and recycling rubbish locally. Such realistic stories are effective in influencing feelings and motivating people to take action.

Journalists make extensive use of visual materials such as photographs and videos to enhance the impact of their information. For example, photographs of polluted beaches or videos of natural disasters allow viewers to better visualize the scale of the problem and evoke strong emotional reactions. In addition, journalists use dramatization and tension-building techniques to draw

attention to environmental issues through headlines and stories about the urgency of the situation. Such techniques bring attention to issues that might otherwise go unnoticed. For instance, the podcast *Floodlines: The story of an unnatural disaster*¹³⁾ presented a detailed account of Hurricane Katrina. The podcast raised the complex issues faced by the residents of New Orleans, and the authors drew the public's attention to the impact of natural disasters, human error and racism on society.

The effectiveness of environmental journalism in influencing public opinion and behaviour is multidimensional and depends on various factors, including the context of messages, channels of dissemination and the characteristics of the target audience. Environmental journalism shapes public opinion about issues, raises awareness and mobilizes action. It also influences people's behaviour by offering practical solutions and inspiring environmentally responsible action. Environmental journalism raises social issues by stimulating public dialogue about the need for change in consumption and production³⁰⁾. The effective impact of environmental journalism depends on its ability to capture audience's attention and evoke an emotional response. Journalists often use visual materials, strong headlines and personal stories to make environmental issues more accessible and meaningful to people. However, it is important that messages are accurate, grounded in science, and avoid exaggeration or misrepresentation to maintain audience trust. In an article from *The Washington Post*, journalists presented an analysis of the effects of the devastating wildfire in Berry Creek, California. The team of journalists provided readers with an interactive experience to engage with the information, which included images of the fire's aftermath, satellite imagery, and detailed analyses of the air currents that directly affected the rate at which the fire spread. Given the large amount of data, the authors identified the climate crisis as one of the key causes of such disasters¹⁵⁾.

In addition to informing, environmental journalism also fosters critical thinking and environmental awareness. Journalists endeavour not only to convey facts, but also to evoke an emotional response and motivation for action. They raise important questions about justice, equal access to resources, and responsibility to future generations, which helps people to better recognize their role in conservation and take an active role in solving environmental problems. Various formats of environmental journalism play an important role in shaping environmental literacy. News articles and reports inform about environmental events and trends, documentaries and video reports visualize issues and deepen understanding, and blogs and social media facilitate the exchange of views and community mobilization. All these formats help audiences to receive a variety of information and develop an understanding of

environmental issues.

3.2. Realizing the concept of sustainable development of society through environmental journalism

The concept of sustainable development, which emerged as a result of the realization of limited natural resources and the need to strike a balance between the economic, social and environmental aspects of development, implies a desire to meet current needs without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. Journalism in this context acts not only as a source of information, but also as a mechanism for shaping public opinion, controlling authorities and stimulating public dialogue. Scholars have concluded that within the framework of environmental journalism, its impact on building environmental literacy and mobilizing the public to address environmental issues becomes particularly important^{31,32)}. Central Asian countries are actively moving towards the SDGs, with Kazakhstan leading the way. Regional cooperation plays a key role in coordinating efforts, and joint adaptation of economic policies, development of sustainable infrastructure and inclusiveness have become priorities in achieving these goals¹⁸⁾.

In June 2022, the second regional SDG Summit for Central Asian countries, entitled "Beyond COVID-19 – Towards Equitable Recovery in Central Asia"¹⁵⁾, was held in Almaty, Kazakhstan. The event was attended by political leaders, international experts, representatives of international organizations and civil society from the region. During the summit, Kazakhstan made a number of commitments, including commitments to the UN, integrating SDG indicators into national development strategies and programmes, and adapting economic policy to global economic change¹⁶⁾. The European Union has expressed its readiness to support Central Asia in achieving the SDGs through investments in infrastructure, skills development and health systems. At the same time, the Central Asia Regional Economic Cooperation programme was initiated to promote cooperative and sustainable development, attracting over USD 30 billion in investments²⁴⁾.

Environmental journalism plays an important role in realizing the principles of sustainable development, including social justice, economic efficiency and environmental integrity³³⁾. In the context of social justice, environmental journalism acts as a voice for disadvantaged and vulnerable groups in society. It highlights issues related to inequalities in access to natural resources, pollution in poor neighbourhoods and the negative impacts of anthropological activities on public health and well-being. Environmental journalism can raise important questions about human rights, social justice and equity in access to environmental benefits, which helps to shape

public consciousness and support the movement towards a more just and sustainable society.

In terms of economic efficiency, environmental journalism identifies examples of successful environmental practices and innovations that promote economic development and facilitate the transition to a green economy. Journalists explore examples of sustainable business models, investments in clean technologies, efficient use of resources and examples of public policies that promote sustainable development³⁴. This information stimulates dialogue between business, government, and society about the need for sustainable economic growth and helps shape strategies to achieve this goal. In terms of environmental integrity, environmental journalism plays the role of observer and protector of nature. It exposes the problems of air, water and soil pollution, destruction of ecosystems, depletion of natural resources and loss of biodiversity.

Environmental journalism can report on the effects of climate change, forest degradation, the threat of species extinction and other environmental crises^{35,36}. By highlighting these issues and identifying the sources of environmental threats, it stimulates public dialogue about the need to conserve nature, take action to protect the environment and move towards sustainable lifestyles.

Thus, environmental journalism plays an important role in implementing the principles of sustainable development by informing, engaging in public dialogue and mobilizing for action to achieve social justice, economic efficiency and environmental integrity. The data presented in Table 1 reflects the key issues that are barriers to sustainable development of society. Addressing these challenges requires joint efforts on the part of governmental and non-governmental organizations, business, and society as a whole.

Table 1: Key challenges on the way to sustainable development of society

Problem	Description
Poverty	About 700 million people live on less than USD 2.15 a day, the extreme poverty line. Extreme poverty remains concentrated in parts of sub-Saharan Africa, fragile and conflict regions and rural areas. The goal of eliminating extreme poverty by 2030 remains unattainable.
Children's health and well-being	In 2019, approximately 5.2 million children under the age of 5 died, mostly from preventable causes. Children aged 1-11 months accounted for 1.5 million of these deaths, and children aged 1-4 years accounted for 1.3 million deaths. New-borns (up to 28 days old) accounted for the remaining 2.4 million deaths.
Inequalities in education	110 million girls and young women could be out of education by 2030. Meeting the goals of reducing maternal mortality and increasing educational opportunities requires action to achieve the goals by 2030.
Gender discrimination	Women hold 27% of parliamentary seats, 36% of local government seats and 28% of leadership positions. It is projected that by 2030, 340 million women and girls will live in extreme poverty. In the labour market, women earn 51 cents for every dollar that men earn.
Water supply and sanitation	2 billion people (26% of the population) do not have access to safe drinking water. 3.6 billion people (46%) lack access to safe sanitation. Between 2 and 3 billion people suffer from water scarcity at least one month a year. Urban populations facing water scarcity are expected to double by 2050.
Climate change and biodiversity loss	Rising levels of greenhouse gases pose serious challenges to ecosystems and human life. The loss of biodiversity threatens the stability of ecosystems and the well-being of all living organisms.
Human rights violations and conflicts	Ongoing conflicts and human rights violations threaten peace and stability. Strengthening the rule of law and protecting human rights are prerequisites for the maintenance of peace and justice.

Source: compiled by the authors.

Environmental journalism plays a key role in shaping public consciousness and activating civic participation in processes aimed at achieving sustainable development. Environmental journalism informs society about the state of the environment and its challenges, including climate change, resource pollution and ecosystem destruction. By providing up-to-date information, journalists promote environmental literacy and awareness-raising. Journalism also acts as a catalyst for public dialogue and the exchange

of ideas on strategies and methods for achieving sustainable development. Journalists identify different perspectives on environmental issues and present multiple viewpoints, which facilitates broad discussion and analysis of issues (Table 2).

Table 2: Environmental journalism methods and approaches to stimulate dialogue and find compromises

Methods and approaches	Description	Examples	Additional information
Diverse selection of information sources	Journalists actively seek out a variety of sources of information and the views of different stakeholders	Inclusion of representatives from academia, governmental and non-governmental organizations, the business sector, activist groups and ordinary citizens	Allows a plurality of opinions to be presented and stimulates discussion
Use of interactive formats	Environmental journalism often uses interactive online platforms, forums, webinars, and social media groups	Providing the audience with the opportunity to participate in the discussion, give feedback, express their opinions and suggestions	Promotes audience engagement and creates an open dialogue
Organization of special projects	Creation of special projects or publications on specific environmental problems or conflicts	Special investigations, series of articles, documentaries aimed at drawing public attention to important environmental issues	Such projects can enhance public dialogue and facilitate the search for compromise solutions
Stakeholder engagement	Journalists actively engage with representatives of various stakeholders through interviews, consultations, and roundtables	Identification of common points of view, search for possible ways to solve the problem	Facilitating a forum for discussion, identifying common interests and developing joint strategies for action

Source: compiled by the authors.

Despite its importance, environmental journalism faces a number of problems and challenges in realizing the concept of sustainable development and finding ways to overcome them. One of the main problems is limited access to information and resources: many environmental issues require in-depth analysis and expert opinion, but access to such information can be limited for several reasons, including restrictions on access to data, lack of funding for research and pressure on journalists from corporations or governments. There is also a lack of public interest in environmental issues and the problem of information manipulation and misinformation. In the context of environmental topics, there may be vested interests that try to distort facts or create misconceptions about issues in order to protect their interests or increase their own profits, which creates challenges for journalists in presenting an objective picture of events. Finally, environmental journalism often faces the problem of lack of attention from editors and publishers. In the face of market competition and declining profits, many media outlets focus on popular and commercially attractive topics, which can lead to environmental issues being ignored or under-reported.

3.3. New trends and directions in environmental journalism

It has been argued that digital technologies and social media play a key role in contemporary environmental journalism, providing new opportunities for reporting on environmental issues and engaging with audiences^{37,38}. One of the main benefits of using digital technologies is the ability to create interactive and multimedia content that allows journalists to visualize complex environmental

processes and issues, making information more accessible and understandable to audiences^{39,40}. Social media also play an important role in disseminating environmental information and engaging audiences: they provide a wide audience reach and allow journalists to reach new audiences and build communities of interest in environmental issues. Social media facilitates feedback and dialogue with audiences, which fosters interactive and dynamic formats for reporting on environmental topics. However, the use of digital technologies and social media also presents challenges. In particular, the risks of manipulating information and spreading misinformation in the online environment need to be taken into account. In addition, it is not always easy to maintain the quality and credibility of content in the fast-paced environment of social media. Despite this, digital technologies and social media represent a powerful tool to enhance public dialogue about environmental issues, raise awareness and mobilize citizen participation in processes aimed at achieving sustainable development of society. The interaction between environmental journalism and the scientific community plays a key role in providing accurate and reliable information on environmental issues. The interaction between these two fields is based on the fact that journalists should work closely with scientists, researchers, and experts to guarantee accurate and reliable information. In addition, collaboration with experts gives journalists access to specialized knowledge and enables them to better understand complex scientific concepts to communicate scientific information to audiences effectively and transparently. Researchers argue that journalists need to have a good understanding of scientific concepts in order to cover environmental issues, and co-

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operation with experts helps them to understand the topic more deeply and present information more accurately⁴¹⁾. In addition, journalists should work closely with experts in the fact-checking process to ensure the accuracy of reported information and avoid misinformation. Expert judgement also helps journalists interpret scientific research and findings in a more accessible way for the public to understand. They help manage the complexity of

a topic and emphasize important nuances, providing more balanced coverage of environmental issues. The symbiotic relationship between environmental journalism and the scientific community ensures that the information delivered to the public is accurate and reliable. The way forward for environmental journalism is to combine joint efforts to overcome existing challenges (Table 3).

Table 3: Recommendations for improving environmental journalism practices

Direction	Recommendations	Examples of implementation and use
Use of innovative technologies	Introducing virtual and augmented reality to create interactive environmental materials.	Using artificial intelligence to personalize content and tailor it to the interests of the audience.
	Application of machine learning algorithms to analyse large data sets and identify environmental trends.	Using blockchain technology for transparency and validation of environmental information.
Interdisciplinary approach	Collaboration with experts from different fields to comprehensively analyse environmental issues.	Studying the impact of environmental problems on human health and developing methods to prevent possible threats.
	Exploring the relationship between environmental change and social and economic processes to identify the root causes of problems.	Analysing the impact of global warming on migration processes and economic stability of regions.
Improving accessibility of information	Creating interactive online platforms with open access to environmental information and exchange of views.	Develop a feedback system for public participation in shaping environmental agendas and priorities.
	Conduct training courses and webinars for journalists and the public on environmental issues and reporting techniques.	Creation of multimedia educational materials for children in order to form an ecological culture among young people.
Cooperation and partnership	Partner with scientific organizations and environmental activists to share information and resources.	Conducting joint research projects between journalists and scientists to identify new environmental problems and their solutions.
	Creating a network of cooperation between different media and journalistic organizations to work together on environmental topics.	Organizing international forums and conferences on environmental issues to exchange experience and transfer best practices.
Use of social media	Actively engage with audiences through social platforms to disseminate environmental information and discuss issues.	Creating online campaigns and challenges that motivate users to take environmental initiatives and change behaviour.
	Using analytical tools to monitor and analyse audience reactions to environmental materials and adapt engagement strategies.	Development of a system for assessing the impact of environmental messages in social media on the formation of environmental consciousness and user behaviour.
Training and development	Organizing training programmes and trainings for journalists on environmental journalism methods and the use of new technologies.	Introduction of educational courses on environmental journalism into the curricula of journalism schools and universities.
	Supporting and stimulating the professional development of environmental journalists through awards, scholarships and international exchanges.	Organizing mentoring programmes for young journalists to help them gain skills and knowledge in environmental journalism.
Combating misinformation	Developing strategies to identify and combat manipulative information in environmental journalism.	Raising journalists' awareness of information manipulation techniques and developing critical thinking skills.
	Implementing a scientific review process for environmental reports to verify the accuracy of information before publication.	Developing guidelines for fact-checking and identifying false information in environmental materials.
Supporting quality projects	Stimulating the creation and support of quality journalistic projects and initiatives on environmental issues.	Allocating grants and funding for independent journalistic investigations in the field of ecology.
	Supporting and encouraging journalists who work to discover and expose environmental problems and offer constructive solutions.	Creating special awards and competitions to highlight outstanding work in environmental journalism.

Source: compiled by the authors.

Improving collaboration between journalists and the scientific community is essential for enhancing the accuracy and reliability of environmental reporting. This can be achieved by establishing formal partnerships and networks between media organizations and scientific institutions, allowing for regular interactions and joint projects. Effective communication is key, with scientists encouraged to present their findings in an accessible manner, free from jargon, and journalists trained to understand and interpret scientific data. Creating directories of experts and data-sharing platforms ensures that journalists have access to the latest research and credible sources. Implementing a scientific review process for environmental reports helps verify the accuracy of information before publication. Additionally, training programs and mentorship initiatives can empower journalists to critically evaluate scientific information and build long-term collaborative relationships with scientists. Both parties should adhere to ethical guidelines to ensure fair and unbiased reporting. By fostering these collaborations, environmental reporting can become more accurate, informative, and impactful, contributing to better public understanding of environmental issues.

Applying the recommendations and strategies suggested in the table will improve the practice of environmental journalism, making it more accessible, informative and attractive to a wide audience.

Local environmental journalism typically concentrates on regional issues that directly affect the communities within a specific area. This type of journalism often covers topics such as local pollution problems, conservation efforts, and environmental initiatives that are relevant to the immediate surroundings. The reporting is usually more granular and personal, focusing on how environmental issues impact the daily lives of local residents. This approach allows for a deeper connection with the audience, as the stories are often relatable and directly relevant to their experiences. Local journalists may also have better access to local sources and can provide more detailed and nuanced coverage of environmental challenges and solutions in their region.

On the other hand, global environmental media addresses broader, worldwide issues that have far-reaching implications. Topics such as climate change, biodiversity loss, and international environmental policies are commonly covered. This type of journalism aims to provide a comprehensive view of environmental challenges that affect the planet as a whole. Global environmental media often involves reporting on international conferences, global initiatives, and scientific research that has worldwide significance^{42,43}. The audience for global environmental media is broader and more diverse, requiring journalists to present information in a way that is accessible and relevant to people from different cultural and geographical backgrounds.

In summary, the impact and reception of environmental journalism in Central Asia are influenced by a complex interplay of cultural attitudes, media capacities, and the region's unique environmental challenges. Effective environmental journalism in this context requires a deep understanding of cultural norms, collaboration across borders, and innovative approaches to engage the public in sustainable practices.

4. Discussion

The study examined the impact of environmental journalism on the formation of environmental literacy and mobilization of society to address environmental issues. The results of the study showed that environmental journalism plays a key role in stimulating public dialogue and monitoring the activities of the authorities in the field of ecology, and the recommendations were aimed at increasing the availability of information, cooperation with the scientific community and the use of social media.

The features of environmental journalism's engagement with the scientific community and society discussed in this paper have been reflected in the diverse ways in which scientific research and expert opinion are used in journalistic reporting. In the context of these findings, a study by A. Nguyen and M. Tran⁴⁴), a systematic literature review of the issues and challenges of science journalism in the Global South, was considered. The reviewed study showed that the main challenges are difficulties in accessing information, difficulties in interacting with the scientific community and limitations in utilizing scientific research in journalistic practice. Further research is recommended to focus on developing effective strategies for overcoming these challenges and assessing their impact on the quality of environmental journalism in different regions.

The journalistic practices and tools revealed in this study, namely providing solutions to problems, the positive aspects of stories and attention to the emotional component of stories, distinguish modern journalism from the traditional news format and can be effective means of improving the quality of journalistic practice and impact on audiences. In a study by J. Mast et al.⁴⁵), it is possible to note similarities in the approach to understanding the role of journalism as an actor of public dialogue and the formation of civic consciousness, and in the work of J. Price⁴⁶) – to taking into account audience needs and interests to create a sustainable model of journalism, which also supported the assertion of the importance of considering user preferences and developing personalized approaches to content delivery for audience retention.

The existing lack of public awareness of concepts such as sustainable development and energy efficiency points to the need for a systematic approach in dealing with information on environmental issues that would provide a

more effective impact on public opinion and behaviour. The work of I. Salovaara⁴⁷⁾ was devoted to studying the impact of digital mapping technologies on contemporary journalism and their role in shaping a new ecology in media space. By comparing the results of the work of the researcher with the results of the conducted research, it is possible to note similarities in the positive attitude and approach to the use of modern technologies in journalism, but also the need for a deeper analysis of the means of communication and their influence on the formation of public consciousness in the field of ecology.

V. Roblek et al.⁴⁸⁾, in turn, provided a comprehensive analysis of the relationship between the Internet, sustainable development and the emergence of Society 5.0, revealing the significance of network technologies in the transition to a sustainable and informatised economy. The study suggests key aspects of the interaction between the Internet and sustainable development, including digital inclusion, education, digital innovation and civic participation, highlighting the need to develop digital technologies and utilize them to achieve sustainable development goals.

The UNESCO (2024) report underscores the escalating dangers environmental journalists face due to their coverage of sensitive environmental issues. These journalists are increasingly subjected to physical attacks, legal harassment, and censorship, often perpetrated by both state and private actors. The report reveals that state entities, such as police and military forces, are responsible for a significant portion of these attacks, highlighting the systemic challenges journalists encounter in seeking protection from the very institutions meant to uphold justice. Private actors, particularly those involved in extractive industries, also pose substantial threats, creating a dual front of risk. Moreover, the prevalence of digital attacks and online harassment, especially targeting women journalists, adds a layer of psychological stress. The lack of accountability for these crimes fosters a climate of impunity, further endangering journalists' safety and compromising their ability to report freely. This multifaceted threat landscape necessitates robust protective measures, legal reforms, and support systems to safeguard the critical work of environmental journalists.

The reviewed studies indicated the interest of the scientific community in environmental journalism. The results pointed to the prospects for productive public dialogue and solving environmental problems with the help of modern methods and approaches to journalism and media dissemination. However, there was a lack of understanding of specific mechanisms of interaction between journalists and experts, as well as unexplored aspects of the impact of environmental journalism on business decisions and the financial sustainability of companies.

5. Conclusions

The study revealed that environmental journalism helps to broaden the readers' outlook and enrich their knowledge of the world around them. It helps people understand the relationship between man and nature, realize the consequences of their actions, and make more responsible decisions in everyday life. The results showed that environmental journalism not only informs but also inspires readers to make the changes necessary to create a sustainable future for all, and its development is a key element in achieving the goals of sustainable development of society by shaping public consciousness and activating civic participation in the processes of raising awareness, stimulating public dialogue and engaging people in active actions to preserve the environment and ensure the well-being of future generations.

As technology and audience tastes change, environmental journalism has evolved new ways for delivering information. Video materials allow journalists to visualize complex environmental processes and events, making information more accessible and understandable to viewers; podcasts allow for in-depth analysis and discussion of environmental topics with experts and interested audiences; and interactives and visualizations make visual materials that help readers understand complex environmental processes. It was determined that the formats evaluated promote environmental coverage, audience involvement, and information dissemination in modern media. The study found that working with scientists and experts allows journalists to investigate complex scientific topics and present them in a way that is accessible to a wide audience, ensuring the credibility of information and its qualitative analysis.

Although the study used valid materials and resources, some aspects of environmental and sustainable development issues may have been left out of the analyses due to limitations in access to information. Since evaluating the effectiveness of environmental journalism is subjective and there have been no longitudinal studies on the real impact of environmental journalism on sustainable development goals, the results of this study represent an initial step in understanding the relationship between environmental journalism and sustainable development. However, despite these limitations, the results show the need for further research and development in this area. Increased access to information, deeper analyses of the impact of environmental journalism on public opinion, and a deeper understanding of the mechanisms of influence on environmental and sustainable development decision-making could be the subjects of future research. Thus, further work in this area is needed to better understand the role of environmental journalism in creating a sustainable and environmentally aware society.

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